

The Command Line GUIde: Graphical Interfaces from Man Pages via AI Technical Supplement

Saketh Ram Kasibatla*, Kiran Medleri Hiremath*, Raven Rothkopf, Sorin Lerner, Haijun Xia, Brian Hempel
{skasibatla, kmedlerihiremath, rrothkopf, lerner, haijunxia, bhempel}@ucsd.edu
University of California San Diego, La Jolla, CA, USA

Fig. 1: Automatically creating a GUIDE-line from a man page.

Abstract—This supplement further details the techniques introduced in our VL/HCC 2025 paper *The Command Line GUIde: Graphical Interfaces from Man Pages via AI* [1]. Namely, we discuss the prompting process to automatically generate an annotated grammar from a man page, and the non-LLM process to convert the annotated grammar into a graphical interface.

This supplement describes details the prompts that we used to automatically generate a GUIDE-line (an annotated grammar) from a man page (Sec. I) and the conversion of a GUIDE-line into a GUI (Sec. II).

I. GUIDE-LINE GENERATION

Figure 1 (reproduced from the main paper) outlines the process of using a large language model (LLM) to generate GUIDE-lines. Figure 3 shows a sample GUIDE-line for the

*Equal contribution.

cat command, and Figure 4 shows the base Ohm grammar from which all GUIDE-lines inherit.

First, we prompt an LLM to generate a test suite containing valid invocations of a command based on its man page. We then use the test suite and man page to generate a draft GUIDE-line. Finally, we use LLM agents to correct syntactic errors, lint the GUIDE-line, and to fix failing test cases. Below, we describe each of these steps in detail.

A. Prompt Structure

For all prompts, we use `claude-3-7-sonnet-20250219` with temperature 1 and thinking tokens. Our process relies on Claude’s long context (200,000 tokens), and its reasoning capabilities. Each prompt consists of a subset the following messages, each of which is formatted using markdown:¹

- a system message, which contains a persona, a task description, and additional task details, such as relevant documentation and specific directions about what to do/avoid.
- a user message² containing few-shot examples for the task in question
- a user message containing invocation-specific inputs
- definitions of tools that the model can invoke

The LLM can respond with a text message, or (if applicable), a *tool call*, which invokes a tool with concrete arguments. In addition to these messages to setup the task, the repair agents (Sections I-D, I-E, I-F, and I-G) contain many alternating tool uses and *tool results*. Tool results contain the output of a tool after it is evaluated by the grammar generation codebase.

B. Generating Test Cases

Test cases are generated in two phases. First, the LLM is prompted to generate 10 valid invocations of a command. It is then asked to generate 10 additional tests to improve test case variety. The system messages for initial test case generation

¹For readability, messages shown in figures will be formatted as rich text, though they are sent to an LLM as the equivalent in markdown.

²all user messages are automatically generated by the grammar generation codebase

and additional test case generation are shown in full in Fig. 5 and Fig. 7 respectively.

Each test case consists of the text to parse (e.g. “ls -lah”) and flags that are expected (e.g. “-l”, “-a”, and “-h”). The LLM outputs these test cases in JSON format by invoking the `output_tests` tool. Sample invocations of initial and additional test case generation are shown in Fig. 6 and Fig. 8. Both prompts do not use any few-shot examples.

C. Generating a Draft GUIDE-line

A draft GUIDE-line is generated by prompting an LLM with a `man` page and test cases as input, and extracting the contents of the first code block with language `ohm` from the response. The system prompt (Fig. 9) for draft GUIDE-line generation includes several sections detailing how to structure a GUIDE-line (“Grammar Format”, “Base Grammar”, “One rule per flag”, and “options rule”) and detailed documentation of the Ohm language (“Builtin Rules”, “inline rule declarations”, and “Lexical rules”). The sections detailing how to structure a GUIDE-line direct the LLM to produce grammars within a *subset* of the Ohm language that is suited for conversion to a GUI, and the sections documenting the Ohm language help prevent common mistakes. These sections are also used in the repair agents’ system messages.

D. Tools for Repair Agents

The 3 repair agents—the syntax repair agent, the linter agent, and the test case repair agent—each use a subset of the following 4 tools:

- `replace(diff)` edits the GUIDE-line, applying the `diff` to the first matching search string, as in other software development agents [2], [3]. In fact, our implementation is a modified version of Cline [3]’s `replace` tool.
- `read()` returns the current GUIDE-line and error message. This helps the agent see the current file state instead of guessing it from the diffs it applied.
- `parse(example, ruleName)` attempts to parse the string `example` under the grammar’s `ruleName` in the current GUIDE-line. This lets an agent debug a problem or test if the problem is fixed.
- `finish()` marks the task as complete and exits the loop, allowing the agent to decide when it is done.

Their tool and argument descriptions are detailed in Fig. 10

E. Repairing Ohm Syntax

The *syntax repair agent* fixes syntax errors (i.e. invalid Ohm grammars) using `read` and `replace`. Its system message (shown in Fig. 11) includes much of the same structure and documentation information from Sec. I-C. It also adds a troubleshooting section which details common mistakes in draft GUIDE-line generation and how to fix them. The agent may perform up to 10 actions. If the agent cannot produce a valid grammar, or the grammar it produces passes zero test cases, we regenerate the GUIDE-line (maximum of 5 retries).

F. Linting a GUIDE-line

The *linter agent* repairs *sequencing errors*. These arise because parsing expression grammars [4], like Ohm, parse alternations (i.e. *or*-clauses) greedily, always taking the first matching rule. Thus, longer rules must precede their prefixes to be matched (e.g. `--print0` must precede `--print`). The linter is instructed to identify and fix sequencing errors, using the `parse` action to test rules and `replace` to fix them. It may perform up to 10 actions or `finish` early.

The linter agent’s system message (Fig. 12) details a concrete example of a sequencing error. It then instructs the agent to (1) list all flags that could cause a sequencing error, (2) use `match` to identify sequencing errors, (3) fix sequencing errors using `replace`, reordering cases in an alternation, and (4) confirm with `match` that the change did in fact fix the sequencing error. Because this agent is instructed to make limited edits, additional documentation for writing Ohm code is not included.

G. Repairing Failing Test Cases

The *test case repair agent* fixes failing tests. As with the linter agent, it uses `parse` and `replace` to debug and fix errors (up to 30 actions). It is run once for each failing test case, and is directed to fix the test and instances of the same issue in other parts of the GUIDE-line. After each run, the edited GUIDE-line is tested against the full test suite, replacing the previous version if it has *strictly fewer* failing tests.

The test case repair agent’s system message (Fig. 13) instructs the agent to use `match` to debug the error and use `replace` to fix the grammar. Notably, it also instructs the agent to fix all other instances of an issue in the grammar, beyond the test case itself. It also instructs the agent to preserve comments annotating arguments and flags.

II. GUI GENERATION

Below we detail how the annotated grammar (the GUIDE-line) is automatically converted into a graphical interface (GUI).

The key difficulty is determining what subgraphs in the grammar represent options. Grammars are often written with abstractions that obscure which terminals should together constitute an option. Consider the grammar of the `cat` command shown in Fig. 2, simplified to only support the `-n/--number` flag to show line numbers and the `-v/--show-nonprinting` flag to show nonprinting characters. Notice, for example, the rule `flag_number_short` is marked as an option, but the rule only matches the single character `"n"`. How does the GUI know that, to add this flag, the text to insert is actually `"-n"` and not just `"n"`?

The key idea is that flags are *optional*, so some ancestor of the flag in the grammar will necessarily be optional: a rule modified by `*` or `?` or `listOf`. Any rules deeper than that modifier can be treated as unit should together form the flag.

To find this flag units and build the GUI, the grammar is traversed top-down and then key information is bubbled

```

BaseCommand {
  // e.g. "-a" or "-abc"
  shortFlags<content> = "-" content+

  // e.g. "--flat"
  longFlag<content> = "--" content

  // files can be a word or a dash (for stdin)
  // { "argument": true, "type": "fileName" }
  file = word
    | "-"
}

Cat <: BaseCommand {
  Start = command

  // Two top-level forms, one with options/files
  // and one bare
  command = "cat" space+ options files?
    | "cat"

  options = listof<option, space+>

  option = longFlag<longFlagContent>
    | shortFlags<shortFlagContent>

  shortFlagContent = flag_number_short
    | flag_showNonprinting_short

  longFlagContent = flag_number_long
    | flag_showNonprinting_long

  // { "option": true, "description": "number all
  // output lines", "short_description": "number all
  // lines", "name": "--number" }
  flag_number_short = "n"

  // { "option": true, "description": "number all
  // output lines", "short_description": "number all
  // lines", "name": "--number" }
  flag_number_long = "number"

  // { "option": true, "description": "use ^ and M-
  // notation, except for LFD and TAB",
  // "short_description": "show nonprinting chars",
  // "name": "--show-nonprinting" }
  flag_showNonprinting_short = "v"

  // { "option": true, "description": "use ^ and M-
  // notation, except for LFD and TAB",
  // "short_description": "show nonprinting chars",
  // "name": "--show-nonprinting" }
  flag_showNonprinting_long = "show-nonprinting"

  files = space+ listof<file, space+>
}

```

Fig. 2: Simplified cat grammar, with some relevant parts of BaseGrammar.

back up from the leaves, with potential modifications by the ancestor rules during the bubble up.

At a terminal-like rule, a single “command alternative” is initialized with:

```

[
  {
    gui: [<terminal string here>],
    option: null,

```

```

    is_optional: false,
    options: [],
  }
]

```

If the rule is annotated as an option, the `option` property will be filled in with the data from the annotation. For example, at the `flag_number_short` rule the GUI to render is simply "n" and it is considered an option:

```

[
  {
    gui: ["n"],
    option: { name: "--number", ... },
    is_optional: false,
    options: [],
  }
]

```

The `is_optional` flag represents whether rule is actually optional based on the grammar structure. It will be modified on bubble up. The empty `options` array comes into play at that point. But first, consider the bubble up one level through the `shortFlagContent` rule. This simply concatenates the alternatives:

```

[
  {
    gui: ["n"],
    option: { name: "--number", ... },
    is_optional: false,
    options: [],
  },
  {
    gui: ["v"],
    option: {
      name: "--show-nonprinting", ...
    },
    is_optional: false,
    options: [],
  }
]

```

One level up is through the application rule `shortFlags<shortFlagContent>`, which was applied (on the downward pass) to be the sequence "-" `shortFlagContent`. For sequences, the alternatives from each subrule are combined with a cross product. In this case, the single alternative from "-" is distributed to the two from `shortFlagContent`, producing:

```

[
  {
    gui: ["-", "n"],
    option: { name: "--number", ... },
    is_optional: false,
    options: [],
  },
  {

```

```

gui: ["-", "v"],
option: {
  name: "--show-nonprinting", ...
},
is_optional: false,
options: [],
}
]

```

If one of the subrules in the sequence was an option, that option info is retained, as above. This is how options are grouped with sibling rules so the option is considered to be e.g. "-n" instead of just "n".

Next, bubbling up through the `option` rule will concatenate the two alternatives for the long version of the flags, producing four alternatives total (not shown).

The next rule, `options = listOf<option, space+>`, is special because the `listOf` form is where the grammar makes the rules below it *actually* optional, since `listOf` means zero or more items. Consequently, all the alternatives are marked `is_optional` so that, as they bubble up, they will be recognized as completed options.

```

[
  {
    gui: ["-", "n"],
    option: { name: "--number", ... },
    is_optional: true,
    options: [],
  },
  {
    gui: ["-", "v"],
    option: {
      name: "--show-nonprinting", ...
    },
    is_optional: true,
    options: [],
  },
  {
    gui: ["--", "number"],
    option: { name: "--number", ... },
    is_optional: true,
    options: [],
  },
  {
    gui: ["--", "show-nonprinting"],
    option: {
      name: "--show-nonprinting", ...
    },
    is_optional: true,
    options: [],
  }
]

```

At sequence rules, like the next rule "cat" `space+ options files?`, the alternatives from the subrules are inspected to see if they contain options

with `is_optional` set to true. If so, rather than distributing the sequence items into the options (as was done above to make "-n" and "-v" from "-" `shortFlagContent`) this location is instead considered to be the point where options may be added and removed. The actually optional options are now considered to be suboptions, they are coalesced together into the `options` property of a single alternative:

```

[
  {
    gui: ["cat", " ", "OPTIONS",
          " ", {arg_type: "fileName"}, " "],
    option: null,
    is_optional: false
    options: [
      { gui: ["-", "n"],
        name: "--number", ... },
      { gui: ["-", "v"],
        name: "--show-nonprinting", ... },
      { gui: ["--", "number"],
        name: "--number", ... },
      { gui: ["--", "show-nonprinting"],
        name: "--show-nonprinting", ... }
    ],
  }
]

```

The special "OPTIONS" flag in the `gui` property indicates where options should be added/removed.

When combined with the other alternative from the `command` rule (bare "cat"), we get the final top-level GUI with two top-level forms, one for `cat` with options and one for bare "cat":

```

[
  {
    gui: ["cat", " ", "OPTIONS",
          " ", {arg_type: "fileName"}, " "],
    option: null,
    is_optional: false
    options: [
      { gui: ["-", "n"],
        name: "--number", ... },
      { gui: ["-", "v"],
        name: "--show-nonprinting", ... },
      { gui: ["--", "number"],
        name: "--number", ... },
      { gui: ["--", "show-nonprinting"],
        name: "--show-nonprinting", ... }
    ],
  },
  {
    gui: ["cat"],
    option: null,
    is_optional: false
    options: [],
  }
]

```

```
}  
]
```

This GUI spec is then post-processed:

- Options with the same `name` identifier are grouped together, so that *e.g.* `"-n"` and `"--number"` are displayed together in the GUI.
- Multiple top-level forms that have exactly identical options are combined, so that the GUI shows those different top-level forms together under a disclosure triangle, with the same shared set of options below. (Not applicable in this example.)

We omit a detailed discussion of how arguments are handled. In short, a rule annotated as an argument is treated at a terminal and produces a simple `{arg_type: "argTypeHere"}` object as its `gui` which bubbles up like any other terminal, *e.g.* the `{arg_type: "fileName"}` shown in the final step of the `cat` example above.

We omit a discussion of how GUI elements are identified (see the `assign_keys` function in the source code) and how GUI state is generated after user text edits to the command (see the `fill_parsed_command_into_gui_model` function in the source code).

REFERENCES

- [1] S. R. Kasibatla, K. Medleri Hiremath, R. Rothkopf, S. Lerner, H. Xia, and B. Hempel, "The Command Line GUIde: Graphical Interfaces from Man Pages via AI," in *IEEE Symposium on Visual Languages and Human-Centric Computing (VL/HCC)*, 2025.
- [2] J. Yang, C. Jimenez, A. Wettig, K. Lieret, S. Yao, K. Narasimhan, and O. Press, "Swe-agent: Agent-computer interfaces enable automated software engineering," *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 37, pp. 50 528–50 652, 2024.
- [3] "Cline - AI autonomous coding agent for VS code," <https://cline.bot/>.
- [4] B. Ford, "Parsing expression grammars: a recognition-based syntactic foundation," in *Proceedings of the 31st ACM SIGPLAN-SIGACT symposium on Principles of programming languages*, 2004.

APPENDIX A

FIGURES FOR GUIDE-LINE GENERATION

- Fig. 3 shows a sample GUIDE-line for `cat`.
- Fig. 4 shows the base grammar from which all GUIDE-lines inherit.
- Fig. 5 shows the system message for generating initial test cases.
- Fig. 6 shows a sample invocation for generating initial test cases.
- Fig. 7 shows the system message for generating additional test cases.
- Fig. 8 shows a sample invocation for generating additional test cases.
- Fig. 9 shows the system message for draft GUIDE-line generation.
- Fig. 9 shows a sample invocation for draft GUIDE-line generation.
- Fig. 10 shows definitions for the `replace`, `read`, `parse`, and `finish` tools used by the syntax repair, linter, and test case repair agents.

- Fig. 11 shows the system message for the syntax repair agent.
- Fig. 12 shows the system message for the linter agent.
- Fig. 13 shows the system message for the test case repair agent.

```

Cat <: BaseCommand {
  Start = command

  // Arguments
  // { "argument": true, "type": "fileName[]", "example": "file1.txt file2.txt" }
  files = nonemptyListOf<file, space+>

  // Options
  options = listOf<option, space+> space+ --some
  | "" --empty

  option = longFlag<longFlagContent>
  | shortFlags<shortFlagContent>ma

  shortFlagContent = flag_showTabsVerbose_short
  | flag_showEndsVerbose_short
  | flag_showNonprinting_short
  | flag_numberNonblank_short
  | flag_squeezeBlank_short
  | flag_showTabs_short
  | flag_showEnds_short
  | flag_showAll_short
  | flag_ignored_short
  | flag_number_short

  longFlagContent = flag_showNonprinting_long
  | flag_numberNonblank_long
  | flag_squeezeBlank_long
  | flag_showTabs_long
  | flag_showEnds_long
  | flag_showAll_long
  | flag_number_long
  | flag_help_long
  | flag_version_long

  // { "option": true, "description": "equivalent to -vET", "short_description": "show all", "common":
  true, "name": "--show-all", "alternate": ["-A"], "requires": [] }
  flag_showAll_short = "A"

  // { "option": true, "description": "equivalent to -vET", "short_description": "show all", "common":
  true, "name": "--show-all", "alternate": ["-A"], "requires": [] }
  flag_showAll_long = "show-all"

  // { "option": true, "description": "number nonempty output lines, overrides -n", "short_description":
  "number nonempty lines", "common": true, "name": "--number-nonblank", "alternate": ["-b"], "requires":
  [] }
  flag_numberNonblank_short = "b"

  // { "option": true, "description": "number nonempty output lines, overrides -n", "short_description":
  "number nonempty lines", "common": true, "name": "--number-nonblank", "alternate": ["-b"], "requires":
  [] }
  flag_numberNonblank_long = "number-nonblank"

  // { "option": true, "description": "equivalent to -vE", "short_description": "show ends with verbose",
  "common": false, "name": "-e", "alternate": [], "requires": [] }
  flag_showEndsVerbose_short = "e"

  // { "option": true, "description": "display $ at end of each line", "short_description": "show line
  endings", "common": true, "name": "--show-ends", "alternate": ["-E"], "requires": [] }
  flag_showEnds_short = "E"

  // { "option": true, "description": "display $ at end of each line", "short_description": "show line
  endings", "common": true, "name": "--show-ends", "alternate": ["-E"], "requires": [] }
  flag_showEnds_long = "show-ends"

  // { "option": true, "description": "number all output lines", "short_description": "number all lines",
  "common": true, "name": "--number", "alternate": ["-n"], "requires": [] }
  flag_number_short = "n"
  ...

```

```

...
// { "option": true, "description": "number all output lines", "short_description": "number all
lines", "common": true, "name": "--number", "alternate": ["-n"], "requires": [] }
flag_number_long = "number"

// { "option": true, "description": "suppress repeated empty output lines", "short_description":
"squeeze blank lines", "common": true, "name": "--squeeze-blank", "alternate": ["-s"], "requires": [] }
flag_squeezeBlank_short = "s"

// { "option": true, "description": "suppress repeated empty output lines", "short_description":
"squeeze blank lines", "common": true, "name": "--squeeze-blank", "alternate": ["-s"], "requires": [] }
flag_squeezeBlank_long = "squeeze-blank"

// { "option": true, "description": "equivalent to -vT", "short_description": "show tabs with verbose",
"common": false, "name": "-t", "alternate": [], "requires": [] }
flag_showTabsVerbose_short = "t"

// { "option": true, "description": "display TAB characters as ^I", "short_description": "show tab
characters", "common": true, "name": "--show-tabs", "alternate": ["-T"], "requires": [] }
flag_showTabs_short = "T"

// { "option": true, "description": "display TAB characters as ^I", "short_description": "show tab
characters", "common": true, "name": "--show-tabs", "alternate": ["-T"], "requires": [] }
flag_showTabs_long = "show-tabs"

// { "option": true, "description": "(ignored)", "short_description": "ignored option", "common": false,
"name": "-u", "alternate": [], "requires": [] }
flag_ignored_short = "u"

// { "option": true, "description": "use ^ and M- notation, except for LFD and TAB",
"short_description": "show nonprinting chars", "common": true, "name": "--show-nonprinting",
"alternate": ["-v"], "requires": [] }
flag_showNonprinting_short = "v"

// { "option": true, "description": "use ^ and M- notation, except for LFD and TAB",
"short_description": "show nonprinting chars", "common": true, "name": "--show-nonprinting",
"alternate": ["-v"], "requires": [] }
flag_showNonprinting_long = "show-nonprinting"

// { "option": true, "description": "display this help and exit", "short_description": "display help",
"common": true, "name": "--help", "alternate": [], "requires": [] }
flag_help_long = "help"

// { "option": true, "description": "output version information and exit", "short_description": "show
version info", "common": true, "name": "--version", "alternate": [], "requires": [] }
flag_version_long = "version"

// Command
command = "cat" space+ options files?
}

```

Fig. 3: A GUIDE-line for the cat command

```

BaseCommand {
  // OPTIONS

  flag<delimiter, content> = delimiter content
  equalsArgument = "=" word

  // a "short" flag is a flag that uses a single dash
  // shortFlags is a single short flag followed by several flag contents (e.g. "-lah")
  shortFlags<content> = flag<"-",content+>

  // shortFlag can only contain a single flag content (e.g. "-l")
  shortFlag<content> = flag<"-",content>

  // a "long" flag is a flag that uses two dashes
  longFlag<content> = flag<"--",content>

  // UTILS

  string = word

  // subcommand can be used to match a command embedded in another command
  // endWord indicates a delimiter (that will not be consumed) at which point the subcommand will stop
  // matching
  // for example, if you'd like to match to the end, use `subcommand<end>`
  // in this example: `command --flag-with-subcommand-arg cat a b c %`, `subcommand<end>` will consume
  // `cat a b c %`.
  // if you'd like to match until "%%", use `subcommand<"%%">`
  // in this example: `command --flag-with-subcommand-arg cat a b c %`, `subcommand<"%%">` will consume
  // `cat a b c`, stopping when it encounters `%`.
  subcommand<endWord> = nonemptyListOf<(~endWord wordIncludingDashes), space+> space+ endWord

  wordIncludingDashes = word --string
  | (~space any)+ -- withDashes

  // files can be a word or a dash (for stdin)

  // { "argument": true, "type": "fileName" }
  file = word
  | "-"

  // a word cannot be a flag (doesn't start with a dash)
  word = ~"- " wordPiece+

  wordPiece = paren --paren
  | quotedString --quoted
  | (~space any)+ --unquoted

  paren = "$(" space* listOf<parenInsides, space+> space* ")" --parenthesized

  parenInsides = quotedString --quoted
  | paren --paren
  | (~space ~")" any)+ -- unquoted

  quotedString = "\" doubleStringCharacter* "\"" --double
  | "'" singleStringCharacter* "'" --single
  | "`" backquotedStringCharacter* "`" --back

  doubleStringCharacter = "\\\" "
  | paren
  | ~("\"") any

  singleStringCharacter = "\\'"
  | paren
  | ~("'" ) any

  backquotedStringCharacter = ~("`") any
  nonParenStringCharacter = ~("(") any

  number = digit+
}

```

Fig. 4: The base Ohm grammar from which all GUIDE-lines inherit

You are an expert programmer. Your task is to take the man page that you are given and produce examples of valid uses of the command, in order to test a grammar for parsing the command.

You will be given a number of test cases and a man page.
Use the 'output_examples' tool to output the examples.

Generate valid examples

Make sure your test cases are valid uses of the command.

Test a variety of syntax

Test a variety of syntax wherever applicable to the man page you are given.

This includes but is not limited to the following options. When generating a test, if you've already used one of the variants that are listed below, *make sure to include the other variants as well*.

- different ways of passing arguments for the same option *generate tests that use all possible variants*. examples below:
 - `--arg=value`: long flag, argument passed using =
 - `-a 5`: short flag, numeric argument separated by a space
 - `-a5`: short flag, numeric argument without a space
- different numbers of arguments (including without arguments where applicable)
- different orders of arguments
- alternate forms of the command

Test embedded commands

IMPORTANT: if the command supports having another command as an argument, make *sure* you include at least one example that tests this.

Only test the command itself

IMPORTANT: Only generate test cases that mention the command itself. Do *not* use pipes ('|'), redirections ('>', '<'), environment variables ('ENV=5 command'), or other commands.

Output format

IMPORTANT: Make *sure* you output an *array of strings*, not a single string.

Fig. 5: System message for generating initial test cases

SYSTEM MESSAGE

You are an expert programmer. Your task is to take the man page that you are given and produce examples of valid uses of the command, in order to test a grammar for parsing the command.

You will be given a number of test cases and a man page.
Use the 'output_examples' tool to output the examples.

...

USER MESSAGE

Number of examples

10

man page

CAT(1)

User Commands

CAT(1)

NAME

cat - concatenate files and print on the standard output

SYNOPSIS

cat [OPTION]... [FILE]...

LLM RESPONSE

```
{
  name: "output_examples",
  input: {
    examples: [{
      "example": "cat file.txt",
      "options": []},
      { "example": "cat -n file.txt",
        "options": ["-n"]},
      ""
    ]
  }
}
```

Fig. 6: Sample invocation for generating initial test cases. See Fig. 5 for the full system message.

You are a senior software engineer. Your colleague, a junior engineer, has written some examples of valid uses of a command for testing a grammar that will parse the command.

You will be given these examples, a number of new examples to add, and a manpage for the command.

Your job is to improve the test suite by adding more tests that are valid uses of the command. Use the 'output_examples' tool to output the examples.

Test a variety of syntax

Test a variety of syntax wherever applicable to the man page you are given.

Make sure you add new tests that test kinds of syntax that are not already present in the existing tests.

This includes but is not limited to the following options. If the existing tests have already used one of the variants that are listed below, *make sure to include the other variants as well*.

- different ways of passing arguments for the same option *generate tests that use all possible variants*. examples below:
 - `--arg=value`: long flag, argument passed using =
 - `-a 5`: short flag, numeric argument separated by a space
 - `-a5`: short flag, numeric argument without a space
 - **IMPORTANT**: if there are tests that pass an argument using `-a 5` style, and if the command supports `-a5` style, make sure to create versions that also pass the same argument using `-a5` style.
- different numbers of arguments (including without arguments where applicable)
- using variables or command substitution to pass arguments

Test prefixed flags

Some commands contain flags that are prefixes of other flags.

For example, `--flag` is a prefix of `--flag-with-arg`.

NOTE: `--iflag` is NOT a prefix of `--flag` since `--iflag` starts with `i` which is not the same as `f` in `--flag`.

Identify all flags that are prefixes of other flags, and add tests that use the longer flags, so that we can check that the grammar can correctly parse the longer flags.

Test embedded commands

Some commands can contain other commands as arguments. If the command supports this, but the current tests do not test this, add tests that do this.

If the command already tests this, add some tests with different delimiters (e.g. `del ↔ 'del'` or `del ↔ \del`) at the end of the command if applicable.

Only test the command itself

IMPORTANT: Only generate test cases that mention the command itself. Do not use pipes (`|`), redirections (`>`, `<`), environment variables (`ENV=5 command`), or other commands.

Output format

IMPORTANT: Make *sure* you output an *array of strings*, not a single string.

Fig. 7: System message for generating additional test cases

SYSTEM MESSAGE

You are a senior software engineer. Your colleague, a junior engineer, has written some examples of valid uses of a command for testing a grammar that will parse the command.

You will be given these examples, a number of new examples to add, and a manpage for the command.

Your job is to improve the test suite by adding more tests that are valid uses of the command.

Use the 'output_examples' tool to output the examples.

...

USER MESSAGE

man page

CAT(1) User Commands CAT(1)

NAME

cat - concatenate files and print on the standard output

SYNOPSIS

cat [OPTION]... [FILE]...

Current tests

- cat file.txt
- cat -n file.txt
- cat --number-nonblank document.txt
- ...

Number of new tests to add

10

LLM RESPONSE

```
{
  name: "output_examples",
  input: {
    examples: [{"example": "cat --number --squeeze-blank output.log",
      "options": ["--number", "--squeeze-blank"]}],
    ...
  }
}
```

Fig. 8: Sample invocation for generating additional test cases. See Fig. 7 for the full system message.

You are an expert programmer who is an expert at writing grammars for the ohm-js library.

You will be given

- a man page
- and a non-comprehensive list of test cases for the command.

Your task is to integrate the information you are given and write an ohm-js grammar that parses the command as described in the man page. This grammar should be able to parse *all* of the flags and options in the man page.

IMPORTANT: BEFORE YOU WRITE ANY RULES, make a **comprehensive** list of **all** flags, options, and arguments in the grammar so you don't miss any options.

Grammar Format

Make sure your grammar consists of 3 sections: the arguments, options, and the command.

Arguments

Make sure that each argument type is preceded with a comment containing a JSON object with the following information:

- argument: true
- type: one of “string”, “directory”, “fileName”, “number”, or “string[]”
- example: an example of a valid string that can be used for this argument

Options

Each option should be preceded with a comment containing a JSON object with the following information:

- option: true
- description: a description of what the option does
- short_description: a summary of description in 4 words or less
- common: true if the option is commonly used, false if not
- name: the name of the command, including characters. If a command has multiple names, choose the longer one for name. This should only include characters and the flag name (e.g. `-A`, `--all`, `-a`, `--append`), and not include anything else (like spaces or arguments e.g. `-A file1.txt`).
- alternate: alternate forms of the command. If a command has shorter forms, they should go here
- requires: other commands that must be enabled to see this command's effect

If the long version of an option has an argument, make sure the short version has the same one.

Make sure that any rule for flag/option that starts with “-” or “--” goes in the options section.

Note that options with a single character and dash that take numeric arguments don't need a space between the dash and the argument. For example, `-c7` and `-c 7` are both valid.

Make sure alternate names for the same flag are listed under the same rule.

IMPORTANT Make sure you include grammar rules for every option and argument mentioned in the man page, without skipping any of them.

Builtin Rules

Ohm comes with a number of builtin rules. You can use these rules in your grammar.

- any: Matches the next Unicode character — i.e., a single code point — in the input stream, if one exists.
- letter: Matches a single character which is a letter (either uppercase or lowercase).
- lower: Matches a single lowercase letter.
- upper: Matches a single uppercase letter.
- digit: Matches a single character which is a digit from 0 to 9.
- hexDigit: Matches a single character which is a either digit or a letter from A-F.
- alnum: Matches a single letter or digit; equivalent to `letter | digit`.
- space: Matches a single whitespace character (e.g., space, tab, newline, etc.)
- end: Matches the end of the input stream. Equivalent to `~any`.
- ~any: Matches any character except the next one in the input stream.
- listOf<elem, sep>: Matches the expression `_elem_` zero or more times, separated by something that matches the expression `_sep_`. E.g., `listOf<letter, ">` will match `'`, `'a'`, and `'a,b,c'`.
- nonemptyListOF<elem, sep>: Like `listOf<elem, sep>`, but matches `_elem_` at least one time.

Base Grammar

On top of the builtin rules, your grammar will inherit from a base grammar whose source is listed below. You can use any rules defined in the base grammar in your grammar.

```
```ohm
${base_grammar}
```
```

Don't reproduce rules from the base grammar

When writing rules, make sure to use existing rules from the base grammar wherever possible.

For example, instead of writing:

```
```ohm
option_shortFlags = "-" shortFlagChar+
```
```

write:

```
```ohm
option_shortFlags = shortFlags<shortFlagChars>
```
```

And instead of trying to recreate the way to parse a command argument:

```
```ohm
commandArg = nonemptyList0f<word, space+>
```
```

make sure you use the existing subcommand rule, which handles more complex cases than you would encounter in the tests.

```
```ohm
commandArg = subcommand<end>
```
```

One rule per flag

IMPORTANT Make sure that you write *at least one rule per flag*, with the appropriate comment before it. DO NOT WRITE ANY OPTIONS OR ARGUMENTS WITHOUT A COMMENT.

instead of writing:

```
```ohm
shortFlagChars = "v" | "u"
```
```

write:

```
```ohm
// { "option": true, "description": "Echo command to be executed before it is
executed", "short_description": "Show executed commands", "common": true, "name": "--
verbose", "alternate": ["-v"], "requires": [], "arguments": [] }
flag_verbose_short = "v"
```
```

```
```ohm
// { "option": true, "description": "Echo command to be executed before it is
executed", "short_description": "Show executed commands", "common": true, "name": "--
unique", "alternate": ["-u"], "requires": [], "arguments": [] }
flag_unique_short = "u"
```
```

```
shortFlagChars = flag_verbose_short | flag_unique_short
```
```

### ***inline rule declarations***

Make sure you add inline rule declarations for all rules with multiple alternates, like this:

```
```ohm
  ForceOpt = "-f" -short
            | "--force" -long
...

```

Lexical rules

Make *all* rules except for Start lexical (i.e. have them start with a lowercase letter).

options rule

Declare the options rule using the format below:

```
```ohm
options = listOf<option, space+> space+ --some
 | "" --empty
...

```

The extra space+ at the end of the “some” case makes sure that there is a space between the options and whatever comes after them.

Fig. 9: System message for generating a draft GUIDE-line. For the full text of the base grammar, see Fig. 4

## SYSTEM MESSAGE

You are an expert programmer who is an expert at writing grammars for the ohm-js library.

You will be given

- a man page
- and a non-comprehensive list of test cases for the command.

Your task is to integrate the information you are given and write an ohm-js grammar that parses the command as described in the man page. This grammar should be able to parse *all* of the flags and options in the man page.

...

## USER MESSAGE: FEW-SHOT EXAMPLES

```
<examples>
 <example>
 <manpage>...</manpage>
 <test_cases>...</test_cases>
 <ideal_output>...</ideal_output>
 </example>
 ...
</examples>
```

## USER MESSAGE: INVOCATION-SPECIFIC CONTEXT

### *man page*

CAT(1)

User Commands

CAT(1)

NAME

cat - concatenate files and print on the standard output

SYNOPSIS

cat [OPTION]... [FILE]...

### *Test Cases*

- cat file.txt
- cat -n file.txt
- cat --number-nonblank document.txt
- ...

## LLM RESPONSE

```
```ohm
Cat <: BaseCommand {
  Start = command

  // Arguments
  // { "argument": true, "type": "fileName[]",
  //   "example": "file1.txt file2.txt" }
  files = nonemptyList0f<file, space+>
  ...
}
```

Fig. 9: Sample invocation for generating a draft GUIDE-line. See Fig. 9 for the full system message.

REPLACE

DESCRIPTION

Request to replace sections of the grammar using SEARCH/REPLACE blocks that define exact changes to specific parts of the file. This tool should be used when you need to make targeted changes to specific parts of a grammar.

ARGUMENTS

diff (string)

One or more SEARCH/REPLACE blocks following this exact format:

```
```\n<<<<<<< SEARCH\n[exact content to find]\n=====\n[new content to replace with]\n>>>>>>> REPLACE\n```\n
```

Critical rules:

1. SEARCH content must match the associated file section to find EXACTLY:
  - Match character-for-character including whitespace, indentation, line endings
  - Include all comments, docstrings, etc.
2. SEARCH/REPLACE blocks will ONLY replace the first match occurrence.
  - Including multiple unique SEARCH/REPLACE blocks if you need to make multiple changes.
  - Include *just* enough lines in each SEARCH section to uniquely match each set of lines that need to change.
  - When using multiple SEARCH/REPLACE blocks, list them in the order they appear in the file.
3. Keep SEARCH/REPLACE blocks concise:
  - Break large SEARCH/REPLACE blocks into a series of smaller blocks that each change a small portion of the file.
  - Include just the changing lines, and a few surrounding lines if needed for uniqueness.
  - Do not include long runs of unchanging lines in SEARCH/REPLACE blocks.
  - Each line must be complete. Never truncate lines mid-way through as this can cause matching failures.
  - To move code: Use two SEARCH/REPLACE blocks (one to delete from original + one to insert at new location)
  - To delete code: Use empty REPLACE section,

## PARSE

### DESCRIPTION

Try matching a substring of the test case against the grammar.  
This tool is useful to help you understand the error better before making changes.  
You can use the match tool multiple times to try different substrings, or different rules.

### ARGUMENTS

<code>substring (string)</code>	The substring of the test case to match against the grammar
<code>ruleName (string)</code>	The name of the rule to match against the substring

## READ

### DESCRIPTION

Read the current version of the grammar, the test case, and the latest error message.  
If you are getting lots of errors while trying to use the "replace" tool, use this tool to double check the current grammar.

## FINISH

### DESCRIPTION

Finish the task.

- before doing this, make sure you've fixed all the issues in the grammar.
- also make sure there are no errors in the grammar.
- if you're not sure if you've fixed all the issues, use the "match" tool to check.

Fig. 10: Tool and argument descriptions for `replace(diff)`, `read()`, `parse(example, ruleName)`, and `finish()`

You are an expert language designer with years of experience working with the ohm-js grammar library.

Your colleague has written an ohm grammar to parse invocations of a cli command, but it has errors.

You will be given

- a manpage for a cli command
- a (potentially broken) ohm grammar for the manpage
- an error with the ohm grammar

Your task is to revise the grammar, fixing errors in the grammar, and adding missing definitions for rules that are used, but not declared.

## ***Documentation***

### ***Syntactic vs. Lexical Rules***

A syntactic rule is a rule whose name begins with an uppercase letter, and lexical rule is one whose name begins with a lowercase letter. The difference between lexical and syntactic rules is that syntactic rules implicitly skip whitespace characters.

In the body of a syntactic rule, Ohm implicitly inserts applications of the spaces rule before each expression. (The spaces rule is defined as spaces = space\*.) As an example, take this fragment of JSON grammar:

```
```ohm
Array = "[" "]" -- empty
      | "[" Elements "]" -- nonEmpty
Elements = Element ("," Element)*
```
```

Array and Elements are both syntactic rules, since their names begin with a capital letter. Here's what a lexical version of these rule would look like, with explicit space skipping:

```
```ohm
array = spaces "[" spaces "]" -- empty
      | spaces "[" spaces elements spaces "]" -- nonEmpty

elements = spaces element (spaces "," spaces element)*
```
```

In terms of the language it accepts, this version of the rules — with explicit space skipping — is equivalent to the syntactic version above.

A few other details that are helpful to know:

If the start rule is a syntactic rule, both leading and trailing spaces are skipped around the top-level application.

When the body of a rule contains a repetition operator (e.g. + or \*), spaces are skipped before each match. In other words, Names = name+ is equivalent to names = (spaces name)+.

Note that no space skipping occurs inside or before the lexical context defined by the # character. That means that this rule will match 'count :33', but not 'count: 33'.

## ***Troubleshooting***

### ***Inconsistent arity***

When you get an error that looks like this:

```
```
Rule ... involves an alternation which has inconsistent arity (expected 4, got 2)
```
```

This is because you have an alternation with different numbers of tokens on the right hand side, such as this one:

```
\`\`
rule = a b c d | a b c
\`\`
```

You can fix this by adding inline rule declarations for each alternative. For example:

```
\`\`
rule = a b c d -- four
 | a b c -- three
\`\`
```

### ***Syntactic vs. Lexical Rules***

When you get an error that looks like this:

```
\`\`
Cannot apply syntactic rule ... from here (inside a lexical context)"
\`\`
```

This is because you are trying to apply a syntactic rule inside a lexical context.

For example, this rule:

```
\`\`ohm
A = "a"
rule = A b c d
\`\`
```

would be an error because A is a syntactic rule and is being applied inside a lexical context.

To fix this, convert the syntactic rule to a lexical rule by making the name lowercase:

```
\`\`ohm
a = "a"
rule = a b c d
\`\`
```

### ***Rule is not declared***

**IMPORTANT:** If you encounter a rule for an option, flag, or argument that is not declared in the grammar, **DO NOT DELETE IT**. Instead, add that rule to the grammar, following the grammar format mentioned below.

### ***Grammar Format***

...

#### ***Builtin Rules***

...

#### ***Base Grammar***

...

#### ***One rule per flag***

...

#### ***Lexical rules***

...

#### ***options rule***

...

Fig. 11: System message for the syntax repair agent. The full versions of sections omitted with ‘...’ can be found in Fig. 9.

You are an expert language designer with years of experience working with the ohm-js grammar library.

Your colleague has written an ohm-js grammar for a command, but it has some issues that prevent it from parsing the command correctly. These issues are described below.

### ***Place longer flags/options before their prefixes in alternation rules***

**TL;DR: if you're having trouble parsing a flag, make sure it comes before its prefixes in alternation rules**

Consider the following grammar:

```
```ohm
option = flag_option
      | flag_option2

flag_option = longFlag<"option">
flag_option2 = longFlag<"option2">
```
```

`match("--option2", "flag_option2")` will succeed, but `match("--option2", "option")` will not.

This is because `flag_option` is a prefix of `flag_option2`, and comes before it in the alternation operator (`|`) in the `option` rule.

To fix this, place longer flags before their prefixes. *This applies to options with arguments as well.*

```
```ohm
option = flag_option2
      | flag_option
```
```

### ***Your Task***

Your task is to fix the grammar by reordering cases of an alternation, in order to fix situations where the grammar cannot match longer options because of the order of rules in the grammar. The section below describes the problem and how to fix it.

You will be given

- an ohm grammar

You have access to the following tools:

- `replace`: to replace sections of the grammar using SEARCH/REPLACE blocks that define exact changes to specific parts of the file.
  - **IMPORTANT**: only change the order of cases in alternation rules. Do not change any other part of the grammar.
- `match`: to match a substring of the test case against the grammar.
- `read`: to read the current version of the grammar, test case, and error message.
- First, make a list of all the flags/options that are prefixes of other flags/options.
- Then, use the `match` tool to test and identify cases where the grammar cannot match longer options because of the order of rules in the grammar. These are cases where the rule for the specific flag/option works, but the rule for the overall option does not with the same string.
  - e.g. `match("--option2", "flag_option2")` will succeed, but `match("--option2", "option")` will not.
- Then, use the `replace` tool to fix the grammar by reordering cases of an alternation.
- Finally, confirm that your fix works by using the `match` tool again.
- Repeat this process for all the cases where the grammar cannot match longer options because of the order of rules in the grammar.

Important Notes:

- After a replace, the user will provide a file's contents directly in their message, in which case you shouldn't use the read tool to get the file contents again since you already have it.
- if you are getting lots of errors while trying to use the "replace" tool, use the "read" tool to double check the current grammar.

Fig. 12: System message for the linter agent

You are an expert language designer with years of experience working with the ohm-js grammar library.

You will be given

- an ohm grammar
- an error with the ohm grammar

your task is to revise the grammar, fixing the error.

You have access to the following tools:

- **replace**: to replace sections of the grammar using SEARCH/REPLACE blocks that define exact changes to specific parts of the file.
  - **match**: to match a substring of the test case against the grammar.
  - **read**: to read the current version of the grammar, test case, and error message.
  - **finish**: to mark the task as complete
    - before doing this, make sure the test case is fixed.
- 
- First, use the match tool to better understand the error. Then, use the replace tool to fix the grammar.
  - The user may provide a file's contents directly in their message, in which case you shouldn't use the read tool to get the file contents again since you already have it.
  - if you are getting lots of errors while trying to use the "replace" tool, use the "read" tool to double check the current grammar.
  - **IMPORTANT** after you fix the issue, look for other places in the grammar with the same issue and fix those as well.

Sometimes, making a change will still result in an error. Keep trying to fix the grammar until you get no errors.

## ***Documentation***

### ***Syntactic vs. Lexical Rules***

...

**IMPORTANT** when adding additional rules to handle parsing of flags, options, or arguments, make sure to duplicate the correct preceding comment for the relevant flag/option/argument. These comments are important annotations in the grammar generation process.

### ***Troubleshooting***

...

#### ***Grammar Format***

...

#### ***Builtin Rules***

...

#### ***Base Grammar***

...

#### ***One rule per flag***

...

#### ***Lexical rules***

...

#### ***options rule***

...

Fig. 13: System message for the linter agent. Full details of the “Troubleshooting” section can be found in Fig. 11, and details of the remaining sections can be found in Fig. 9